

The arc length of power- and exponential functions

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2017

We view the following figure:

We search the arc length of this function. The general formula in the plane can be written:

$$L = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{1 + f'(x)^2} dx$$

The function has got the form: $f(x) = a \cdot x^n$ $a > 0$ $n \in \mathbb{N}_0$

with the differentiation: $f'(x) = n \cdot x^{n-1} \cdot a$

The case $n=0$:

It follows $f(x)=a$ and $f'(x)=0$ thus :

$$L = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} 1 dx = x_2 - x_1$$

The case n=1:

We get $f(x)=ax$ and $f'(x)=a$ we yield:

$$L = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{1+a^2} dx = \sqrt{1+a^2} \cdot (x_2 - x_1)$$

The general arc length of power functions:

$$L = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{1 + n^2 \cdot a^2 \cdot x^{2n-2}} dx$$

Because of a theorem of Mangoldt-Knopp [1] p.51ff integrals of the form:

$$\int x^\alpha \cdot (a + b x^\beta)^\gamma dx$$

have got a representation in a closed form, if the exponents α, β, γ are rational numbers and if at least one of the three numbers $\frac{\alpha+1}{\beta}, \gamma, \frac{\alpha+1}{\beta} + \gamma$ is integer. In the case $n=2$

the condition is true, but not in the case $n>2$.

Now we view the case $n=2$:

The following formula of the arc length is valid:

$$L = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{1 + 4 \cdot a^2 \cdot x^2} dx$$
$$= \left[\frac{\operatorname{arcsinh}(2ax)}{4a} + \frac{x \cdot \sqrt{4a^2x^2 + 1}}{2} \right]_{x_1}^{x_2} = [F(x)]_{x_1}^{x_2}$$

Proof with differentiation:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\operatorname{arcsinh}(2ax)}{4a} \right) = \frac{1}{2 \cdot \sqrt{4a^2x^2 + 1}}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{x \cdot \sqrt{4a^2x^2 + 1}}{2} \right) = \frac{\sqrt{4a^2x^2 + 1}}{2} + \frac{2a^2x^2}{\sqrt{4a^2x^2 + 1}}$$

Sum of the differentiations with the value: $A := 4a^2x^2 + 1$

$$F'(x) = \frac{1 + A + 4 \cdot a^2 \cdot x^2}{2 \cdot \sqrt{A}} = \frac{2 \cdot A}{2 \cdot \sqrt{A}} = \sqrt{A}$$

The differentiation is equal to the integrand. The proof is ready.

Now we use the general exponential function: $f(x) = b \cdot a^{mx}$

with the differentiation: $f'(x) = b \cdot a^{mx} \cdot m \cdot \ln a$

We have the following assumption:

$$L = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{1 + b^2 m^2 (\ln a)^2 \cdot a^{2mx}} dx$$

$$= \left[\frac{1}{2 \cdot \ln a \cdot m} \cdot \ln \left(\frac{\sqrt{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1} - 1}{\sqrt{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1} + 1} \right) \right]$$

$$+ \left. \frac{\sqrt{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1}}{\ln a \cdot m} \right]_{x_1}^{x_2} = [F(x)]_{x_1}^{x_2}$$

Proof with differentiation and a law for logarithms:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\ln(\sqrt{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1} - 1)}{2 \cdot \ln a \cdot m} \right)$$

$$= \frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot a^{2mx} \cdot (\ln a)^2 \cdot b^2 \cdot m^2}{(a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1)^{0.5} \cdot \left((a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1)^{0.5} - 1 \right)}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\ln(\sqrt{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1} + 1)}{2 \cdot \ln a \cdot m} \right)$$

$$= \frac{\frac{1}{2} \cdot a^{2mx} \cdot (\ln a)^2 \cdot b^2 \cdot m^2}{(a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1)^{0.5} \cdot \left((a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1)^{0.5} + 1 \right)}$$

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{\sqrt{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1}}{\ln a \cdot m} \right) = \frac{a^{2mx} \cdot (\ln a)^2 \cdot b^2 \cdot m^2}{\sqrt{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1}}$$

We use the value: $A := a^{2mx} \cdot (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 + 1$

Sum rule and difference rule:

$$\begin{aligned} F'(x) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2}{\sqrt{A} \cdot (\sqrt{A} - 1)} - \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2}{\sqrt{A} \cdot (\sqrt{A} + 1)} \\ &\quad + \frac{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2}{\sqrt{A}} \\ &= \frac{a^{2mx} \cdot (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 \cdot \left[\frac{1}{2} \cdot (\sqrt{A} + 1) - \frac{1}{2} (\sqrt{A} - 1) + (\sqrt{A} + 1) \cdot (\sqrt{A} - 1) \right]}{\sqrt{A} \cdot (\sqrt{A} - 1) \cdot (\sqrt{A} + 1)} \\ &= \frac{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 \cdot (1 + A - 1)}{\sqrt{A} \cdot (\sqrt{A} - 1) \cdot (\sqrt{A} + 1)} \\ &= \frac{a^{2mx} (\ln a)^2 b^2 m^2 \cdot \sqrt{A}}{A - 1} = \sqrt{A} \end{aligned}$$

The differentiation is equal to the integrand, the proof is done.

References:

[1] Mangoldt-Knopp: Einführung in die höhere Mathematik Band II